

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

ANALYSIS OF THE POSSIBILITIES OF CONSTRUCTING A COMMUTATIVE VECTOR ALGEBRA

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ABSTRACT

The practical application of vector algebra and quaternion algebra has given scientists good opportunities to solve a wide range of fundamental and applied scientific and technological problems. As is known, one of the most important properties in number theory is the property of commutativity. Until now, it was believed that only algebras of real and complex numbers have the property of commutativity. The well-known theorems of Frobenius and Hurwitz state that algebras of quaternions and other hypercomplex numbers cannot have the property of commutativity. In this paper, we indicate the conditions for ensuring commutativity and prove that the commutativity of the orthogonal product of two two-dimensional vectors and the commutativity of the quaternion algebra can be ensured by taking into account the directions of the orthogonal and collinear components of one vector relative to the linear direction of the other vector.

Keywords: vector, quaternion, algebra, multiplication, commutativity.

MSC: 11R52, 15A03, 53A45

1. Introduction.

Currently, such branches of mathematics as vector algebra and number theory are widely used to conduct effective theoretical studies of the properties and features of various physical, technological and other processes [1-19]. Analysis of the possibilities for improving these and other branches of mathematics have always been and are still relevant issues. For example, in 1843, Hamilton developed and proposed quaternion algebra and vector algebra. Note that before that, many famous mathematicians studied the possibilities and worked on the problem of expanding the algebra of complex numbers and developing the algebra of multi-dimensional numbers. The development and application of vector algebra and quaternion algebra in practice gave scientists good opportunities for solving a wide range of fundamental and applied scientific and technological problems [20-32]. One of the most important properties in number theory is the property of commutativity. Until now, it is believed that only algebras of real and complex numbers have the property of commutativity. The well-known theorems of Frobenius and Hurwitz state that algebras of quaternions and other hypercomplex numbers cannot have the property of commutativity [27]. It should be noted that for many years no work on an in-depth critical analysis of these theorems was carried out, and therefore there were no noticeable attempts to develop commutative algebras of hypercomplex numbers. However, in [18] conditions for ensuring commutativity are indicated and a proof is given of the possibility of constructing a commutative algebra of hypercomplex numbers with division over the field of real numbers.

2. Materials and Methods. Properties of product of two-dimensional vectors.

This article continues the study of problems of ensuring the commutativity of products of vectors and quaternions. First, we will consider the proofs of the following theorems.

Theorem 1. A complex number is a mapping of a two-dimensional vector with respect to the scalar direction.

Theorem 2. The commutativity of the orthogonal product of two two-dimensional vectors can be ensured by taking into account the directions of the orthogonal and collinear components of one vector relative to the linear direction of another vector.

Proof. An arbitrary vector \vec{r}_n in space can be represented by the following formula

$$\vec{r}_n = r_n \vec{e}_n. \quad (1)$$

Here r_n denotes the value of the module of the vector, \vec{e}_n - is a unit vector indicating the direction of the vector in the space under consideration, the index n - is the number of a specific vector. Note that the unit vector \vec{e}_n satisfies the condition $(\vec{e}_n)^2 = 1$.

Consider a pair of vectors and write them in the form proposed above by the formula (1)

$$\vec{r}_1 = r_1 \vec{e}_1, \quad \vec{r}_2 = r_2 \vec{e}_2. \quad (2)$$

A vector \vec{r}_2 relative to a vector \vec{r}_1 can be represented as a sum of mutually orthogonal vectors, one of which is the projection of the vector \vec{r}_2 onto the vector direction \vec{r}_1 , and the other is perpendicular to this direction, that is, in the form

$$\vec{r}_2 = r_2 \vec{e}_2 = r_2 \left[\vec{e}_1 \cos(\hat{\vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2}) + \vec{e}_1^\perp \sin(\hat{\vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2}) \right] \quad (3)$$

Let us denote here

$$\varphi_{12} = (\hat{\vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2}).$$

Then from (3) we have

$$\vec{e}_2 = \vec{e}_1 \cos \varphi_{12} + \vec{e}_1^\perp \sin \varphi_{12}. \tag{4}$$

Expression (4) is squared

$$\begin{aligned} (\vec{e}_2)^2 &= (\vec{e}_1 \cos \varphi_{12} + \vec{e}_1^\perp \sin \varphi_{12})(\vec{e}_1 \cos \varphi_{12} + \vec{e}_1^\perp \sin \varphi_{12}) = \\ &= \cos^2 \varphi_{12} + \sin^2 \varphi_{12} + (\vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_1^\perp + \vec{e}_1^\perp \vec{e}_1) \cos \varphi_{12} \sin \varphi_{12}. \end{aligned}$$

Considering that here

$$(\vec{e}_2)^2 = (\vec{e}_n)^2 = 1, \quad \cos^2 \varphi_{12} + \sin^2 \varphi_{12} = 1,$$

we get

$$\vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_1^\perp + \vec{e}_1^\perp \vec{e}_1 = 0, \quad \vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_1^\perp = -\vec{e}_1^\perp \vec{e}_1. \tag{5}$$

From (5) it follows

$$(\vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_1^\perp)^2 = \vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_1^\perp \vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_1^\perp = \vec{e}_1 (-\vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_1^\perp) \vec{e}_1^\perp = -\vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_1^\perp \vec{e}_1^\perp = -1. \tag{6}$$

Next, consider equation (3) in more detail

$$\vec{r}_2 = r_2 \vec{e}_2 = r_2 (\vec{e}_1 \cos \varphi_{12} + \vec{e}_1^\perp \sin \varphi_{12}) = r_2 \vec{e}_1 \left(\cos \varphi_{12} + \frac{1}{\vec{e}_1} \vec{e}_1^\perp \sin \varphi_{12} \right).$$

Here, $\frac{1}{\vec{e}_1} \vec{e}_1^\perp = \vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_1^\perp$, as well as from (6) follows $\vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_1^\perp = i$. Therefore, the last equation can be written as

$$\vec{r}_2 = r_2 \vec{e}_1 (\cos \varphi_{12} + i \sin \varphi_{12}). \tag{7}$$

From (7) we can conclude that the complex number is a mapping of a two-dimensional vector with respect to the scalar direction. In this case, the direction of the unit vector \vec{e}_1 is scalar. **Theorem 1 is proved.**

The angle $\varphi_{12} = \left(\vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2 \right)$ in equation (7) is measured around the origin point in the direction from the unit vector \vec{e}_1 to the unit vector \vec{e}_2 . When counting this angle in the opposite direction, we have

$$\varphi_{21} = \left(\vec{e}_2, \vec{e}_1 \right) = - \left(\vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2 \right) = -\varphi_{12}. \tag{8}$$

Taking into account (8), equation (7) can be represented as

$$\vec{r}_2 = r_2 \vec{e}_1 (\cos \varphi_{21} - i \sin \varphi_{21}). \tag{9}$$

Remark 1. It is easy to see from (7) and (9) that the complex conjugate numbers differ only in the direction of the angle between the same vectors.

In general, the product of two coplanar vectors relative to the same common direction is a complex number. For example,

$$\vec{r}_1 \vec{r}_2 = r_1 \vec{e}_1 r_2 \vec{e}_1 (\cos \varphi_{12} + i \sin \varphi_{12}) = r_1 r_2 (\cos \varphi_{12} + i \sin \varphi_{12}). \tag{10}$$

Here both vectors are referenced and are presented with respect to the direction of the unit vector \vec{e}_1 .

Let's move on from the polar coordinate system to the two-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system x, y , for this we accept

$$\vec{e}_1 = \vec{e}_x, \vec{e}_1^\perp = \vec{e}_y, \vec{e}_2 = \vec{e}_n. \tag{11}$$

Taking into account (11), equation (4) takes the form

$$\vec{e}_n = \vec{e}_x \cos \left(\vec{e}_x, \vec{e}_n \right) + \vec{e}_y \sin \left(\vec{e}_x, \vec{e}_n \right). \tag{12}$$

Additionally designating

$$\left(\vec{e}_x, \vec{e}_n \right) = \varphi_{xy}^n, \tag{13}$$

from (12) we get

$$\vec{e}_n = \vec{e}_x \cos \varphi_{xy}^n + \vec{e}_y \sin \varphi_{xy}^n. \tag{14}$$

Using (11) - (14) an arbitrary vector in a two-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system in canonical form can be represented as

$$\vec{r}_n = r_n \vec{e}_n = r_n \left[\vec{e}_x \cos \left(\vec{e}_x, \vec{e}_n \right) + \vec{e}_y \sin \left(\vec{e}_x, \vec{e}_n \right) \right] = r_n (\vec{e}_x \cos \varphi_{xy}^n + \vec{e}_y \sin \varphi_{xy}^n) = x_n \vec{e}_x + y_n \vec{e}_y. \tag{15}$$

As noted above, the vector (15) is related to the complex number by the following equation

$$x_n + iy_n = \vec{e}_x (x_n \vec{e}_x + y_n \vec{e}_y).$$

From expressions (11) and (14) it follows

$$\vec{e}_x \vec{e}_y = -\vec{e}_y \vec{e}_x. \tag{16}$$

Formula (16) is practically a copy of formula (5) in the considered two-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system.

When multiplying two vectors \vec{r}_a and \vec{r}_b the product of unit vectors, instead of the canonical form of equation (16), it should be represented in a more general form

$$\vec{e}_x^a \vec{e}_y^b = -\vec{e}_y^b \vec{e}_x^a = \vec{e}_y^b \vec{e}_x^a. \tag{17}$$

In (17), the subscripts indicate the direction of the angles in the coordinate system used, and the superscripts show from the direction of which vector the angle between the vectors is actually measured when they are multiplied. Note that the indices of the first multiplier indicate the directions from which the angle between the vectors is counted.

The product of unit vectors (17) to the second degree has the form

$$\left(\vec{e}_x^a \vec{e}_y^b \right)^2 = \vec{e}_x^a \vec{e}_y^b \vec{e}_x^a \vec{e}_y^b = \vec{e}_x^a (-\vec{e}_x^b \vec{e}_y^a) \vec{e}_y^b = -\vec{e}_x^a \vec{e}_x^b \vec{e}_y^a \vec{e}_y^b = -(\vec{e}_x)^2 (\vec{e}_y)^2 = -1. \tag{18}$$

Taking into account (17) and (18), the product of unit vectors can be represented as

$$\vec{e}_x^a \vec{e}_y^b = i e_{xy}^{ab}. \tag{19}$$

Here $i^2 = -1$, $(e_{xy}^{ab})^2 = 1$. Besides,

$$e_{xy}^{ab} = -e_{yx}^{ab} = -e_{xy}^{ba} = e_{yx}^{ba}. \quad (20)$$

Equation (20) follows from (17) and (19).

Let us now consider in more detail the product of two vectors \vec{r}_a and \vec{r}_b

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{r}_a \vec{r}_b &= r_a r_b \vec{e}^a \vec{e}^b = r_a r_b (\vec{e}_x^a \cos \varphi_{xy}^a + \vec{e}_y^a \sin \varphi_{xy}^a) (\vec{e}_x^b \cos \varphi_{xy}^b + \vec{e}_y^b \sin \varphi_{xy}^b) = \\ &= r_a r_b (\vec{e}_x^a \vec{e}_x^b \cos \varphi_{xy}^a \cos \varphi_{xy}^b + \vec{e}_y^a \vec{e}_y^b \sin \varphi_{xy}^a \sin \varphi_{xy}^b + \vec{e}_x^a \vec{e}_y^b \cos \varphi_{xy}^a \sin \varphi_{xy}^b + \vec{e}_y^a \vec{e}_x^b \sin \varphi_{xy}^a \cos \varphi_{xy}^b) = \\ &= r_a r_b [\cos(\varphi_{xy}^b - \varphi_{xy}^a) + i e_{xy}^{ab} \sin(\varphi_{xy}^b - \varphi_{xy}^a)]. \end{aligned}$$

Here the first multiplier is the vector \vec{r}_a . Let us further consider the product of the same vectors in the case when the first multiplier is the vector \vec{r}_b

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{r}_b \vec{r}_a &= r_a r_b \vec{e}^b \vec{e}^a = r_a r_b (\vec{e}_x^b \cos \varphi_{xy}^b + \vec{e}_y^b \sin \varphi_{xy}^b) (\vec{e}_x^a \cos \varphi_{xy}^a + \vec{e}_y^a \sin \varphi_{xy}^a) = \\ &= r_a r_b (\vec{e}_x^b \vec{e}_x^a \cos \varphi_{xy}^b \cos \varphi_{xy}^a + \vec{e}_y^b \vec{e}_y^a \sin \varphi_{xy}^b \sin \varphi_{xy}^a + \vec{e}_x^b \vec{e}_y^a \cos \varphi_{xy}^b \sin \varphi_{xy}^a + \vec{e}_y^b \vec{e}_x^a \sin \varphi_{xy}^b \cos \varphi_{xy}^a) = \\ &= r_a r_b [\cos(\varphi_{xy}^a - \varphi_{xy}^b) + i e_{xy}^{ba} \sin(\varphi_{xy}^a - \varphi_{xy}^b)] = \\ &= r_a r_b [\cos(\varphi_{xy}^b - \varphi_{xy}^a) + i(-e_{xy}^{ab}) \sin(-1)(\varphi_{xy}^b - \varphi_{xy}^a)] = \\ &= r_a r_b [\cos(\varphi_{xy}^b - \varphi_{xy}^a) + i e_{xy}^{ab} \sin(\varphi_{xy}^b - \varphi_{xy}^a)]. \end{aligned}$$

Comparison of the two obtained results shows that the complete product of two vectors has the commutativity property

$$\vec{r}_a \vec{r}_b = \vec{r}_b \vec{r}_a. \quad (21)$$

Theorem 2 is proved.

Note that the complete product of two vectors (21) can be represented as

$$\vec{r}_a \vec{r}_b = \vec{r}_a \cdot \vec{r}_b + \vec{r}_a \times \vec{r}_b, \quad (22)$$

where

$$\vec{r}_a \cdot \vec{r}_b = r_a r_b \cos(\varphi_{xy}^b - \varphi_{xy}^a) \quad (23)$$

is the scalar (collinear) product of vectors, and the orthogonal product

$$\vec{r}_a \times \vec{r}_b = i e_{xy}^{ab} r_a r_b \sin(\varphi_{xy}^b - \varphi_{xy}^a) \quad (24)$$

differs from the vector product formula accepted in modern vector algebra only by the coefficient $i e_{xy}^{ab}$, which confirms that the complete product of two-dimensional vectors is a complex number and in the vector product it is necessary to correctly take into account the directions of counting the angles between the multiplier vectors. In addition, equations (20) and (24) confirm that, with careful consideration of the directions of the angles between the multipliers, the vector product has the commutativity property.

Remark 2. In a vector product, the third direction for the product of unit vectors is not the third linear direction perpendicular to the directions of the multipliers, but the direction of counting the angles between the vectors.

3. Results. The commutativity of the quaternion algebra.

Theorem 3. The commutativity of the product of quaternions can be ensured by observing the correct rules for taking into account the directions of the angles between the coplanar vector components of the quaternions, which are orthogonal to the scalar direction.

Proof. In the Cartesian coordinate system, the complete product of vectors \vec{r}_a and \vec{r}_b has the form

$$\vec{r}_a \vec{r}_b = (x_a \vec{e}_x^a + y_a \vec{e}_y^a) (x_b \vec{e}_x^b + y_b \vec{e}_y^b) = x_a x_b + y_a y_b + i e_{xy}^{ab} (x_a y_b - x_b y_a), \quad (25)$$

where the scalar and cross products are expressed by the following equations

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{r}_a \cdot \vec{r}_b &= x_a x_b + y_a y_b, \\ \vec{r}_a \times \vec{r}_b &= i e_{xy}^{ab} (x_a y_b - x_b y_a). \end{aligned}$$

Now let's analyze what quantitative numerical parameters and signs of directions characterize the two-dimensional vectors $\vec{r}_n = x_n \vec{e}_x^n + y_n \vec{e}_y^n$ considered above and their full product. From the given vector formula and equation (25), it can be seen that two-dimensional vectors and their product contain the following components:

- scalar component, represented by real numbers, which can be associated with the direction in space, which is chosen as the base (scalar) direction;
- vector components characterizing the values of projections of vectors in the coordinate directions x and y , orthogonal to the base (scalar) direction;
- a planar-vector component that allows you to determine the reference directions and the angles between the vectors in the plane xy , that is, in the same coordinate directions x and y orthogonal to the base (scalar).

Taking into account the components listed above for two-dimensional vectors and their product, and considering a scalar number as a quantitative characteristic of a separate (scalar) direction, we can expand the dimension of the mapped vector space and represent the extended analog of the complex number for this vector space in the following form

$$q = x_0 + i(x_1 e_1 + x_2 e_2 + x_{12} e_{12}), \quad (26)$$

where x_0, x_1, x_2, x_{12} – real numbers, $i^2 = -1$, $e_1^2 = e_2^2 = e_{12}^2 = 1$, $e_{12} = e_1 e_2 = -e_2 e_1 = -e_{21}$.

Equation (26) can also be represented as the following four-component number

$$q = x_0 + i e_1 x_1 + i e_2 x_2 + i e_{12} x_{12} = x_0 + i_1 x_1 + i_2 x_2 + i_{12} x_{12},$$

here $i_1^2 = i_2^2 = i_{12}^2 = -1$.

The conjugate number to the reduced four-component number, providing division over the field of real numbers, has the form

$$\bar{q} = x_0 - i_1x_1 - i_2x_2 - i_{12}x_{12}.$$

In essence, the four-component number given in (26) is a quaternion whose algebra, as will be shown below, has the commutativity property. Here, the quaternion, being a four-component number, characterizes the three-dimensional space, since the component $x_{12}e_{12}$ in equation (26) belongs to the plane x_1x_2 and linearly describes the directions and angles between pairs of vectors on this plane.

Note that a quaternion in three-dimensional space is associated with a four-component composite vector

$$\vec{r} = x_0\vec{e}_0 + x_1\vec{e}_1 + x_2\vec{e}_2 + x_{12}\vec{e}_{12}, \tag{27}$$

where \vec{e}_0 corresponds to the scalar direction; \vec{e}_1 and \vec{e}_2 are orthogonal to each other radial unit direction vectors in the plane x_1x_2 , which is orthogonal to the scalar direction; \vec{e}_{12} displays the tangential direction in the plane x_1x_2 , that is, the direction of the unit vector \vec{e}_{12} is planar orthogonal to the radial direction in the specified plane.

It is easy to see that quaternion (26) can be obtained from (27) by multiplying both parts of this equation by \vec{e}_0 , that is $q = \vec{e}_0\vec{r}$. When multiplying the right side of equation (27) on \vec{e}_0 , it is taken into account that

$$\vec{e}_0^2 = 1, \vec{e}_0\vec{e}_1 = ie_1, \vec{e}_0\vec{e}_2 = ie_2, \vec{e}_0\vec{e}_{12} = ie_{12}.$$

Consider now the product of two quaternions

$$\begin{aligned} q_aq_b &= [x_0^a + i(x_1^ae_1^a + x_2^ae_2^a + x_{12}^ae_{12}^a)][x_0^b + i(x_1^be_1^b + x_2^be_2^b + x_{12}^be_{12}^b)] = \\ &= x_0^ax_0^b - (x_1^ax_1^be_1^ae_1^b + x_2^ax_2^be_2^ae_2^b + x_{12}^ax_{12}^be_{12}^ae_{12}^b) + i(x_0^ax_1^be_1^b + x_0^bx_1^ae_1^a + x_{12}^ax_2^be_2^ae_2^b + x_2^ax_{12}^be_2^ae_2^b) + \\ &\quad + i(x_0^ax_2^be_2^b + x_0^bx_2^ae_2^a + x_{12}^ax_1^be_{12}^be_1^b + x_1^ax_{12}^be_{12}^ae_1^a) + i(x_0^ax_{12}^be_{12}^b + x_0^bx_{12}^ae_{12}^a + x_1^ax_2^be_1^ae_2^b + \\ &\quad x_2^ax_1^be_2^ae_1^b). \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

When performing the multiplication in (28), the following conditions must be taken into account

$$\begin{aligned} e_1^a &= e_1^b = e_1, e_2^a = e_2^b = e_2, e_{12}^a = e_{12}^b = e_{12}, \\ e_1^ae_2^b &= -e_1^be_2^a = -e_2^ae_1^b = e_2^be_1^a = e_{12}, e_1^ae_{12}^b = -e_{12}^ae_1^b = -e_1^be_{12}^a = e_{12}^be_1^a = e_2, \\ e_{12}^ae_2^b &= -e_{12}^be_2^a = -e_2^be_{12}^a = e_2^ae_{12}^b = e_1, e_1^2 = e_2^2 = e_{12}^2 = 1. \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

From (28) and (29) it follows that the product of the quaternions under consideration has the property of commutativity

$$\begin{aligned} q_aq_b &= [x_0^a + i(x_1^ae_1^a + x_2^ae_2^a + x_{12}^ae_{12}^a)][x_0^b + i(x_1^be_1^b + x_2^be_2^b + x_{12}^be_{12}^b)] = \\ &= x_0^ax_0^b - (x_1^ax_1^b + x_2^ax_2^b + x_{12}^ax_{12}^b) + i[(x_0^ax_1^b + x_0^bx_1^a + x_{12}^ax_2^b - x_2^ax_{12}^b)e_1 + \\ &\quad + (x_0^ax_2^b + x_0^bx_2^a + x_{12}^ax_1^b - x_1^ax_{12}^b)e_2 + (x_0^ax_{12}^b + x_0^bx_{12}^a + x_1^ax_2^b - x_2^ax_1^b)e_{12}] = q_bq_a. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3 is proved.

4. Discussion

Based on the results obtained above, we can draw conclusions in the form of the following remarks:

Remark 3. As in the theory of complex variables, quaternion (26) has a conjugate four-dimensional number in the form

$$\bar{q} = x_0 - i(x_1e_1 + x_2e_2 + x_{12}e_{12}). \tag{30}$$

The product of conjugate quaternions (26) and (30) is

$$q\bar{q} = x_0^2 + x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_{12}^2. \tag{31}$$

Remark 4. Equations (28) - (31) confirm that the quaternion algebra (26) is a commutative division algebra over the field of real numbers.

In recent years, much attention has been paid in the field of information systems to the study and use of quantum technologies in processing and transmitting information [33, 34]. The results of this paper make it possible to construct new commutative algebras of multidimensional hypercomplex numbers with division over the field of real numbers and can find wide application in developing new efficient algorithms for quantum cryptography and the quantum Internet. Note that, based on the proof of the above theorems, it was shown that the commutativity of the algebras considered in this paper is their important fundamental property. Due to space limitations, the author does not show methods for constructing commutative algebras of various multidimensional hypercomplex numbers with a large number of dimensions in this article. The author plans to present these results in subsequent papers.

5. Conclusion.

In this paper, we consider the problems of ensuring the commutativity of the vector product and the quaternion algebra. We present proofs that the commutativity of the orthogonal product of two two-dimensional vectors can be ensured by taking into account the directions of the orthogonal and collinear components

of one vector relative to the linear direction of the other vector. The commutativity of the quaternion algebra can be ensured by observing the correct rules for taking into account the directions of the angles between coplanar vector components of quaternions that are orthogonal to the scalar direction. Using the method proposed in this paper, the author of this paper continued to consider the problems of developing hypercomplex numbers with a higher dimension, the algebras of which have the property of commutativity of multiplication and the property of division over the field of real numbers. The results obtained can find application in solving a number of fundamental and applied problems in various fields of science and technology.

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Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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